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[Reputational Risk and Firm Performance: The Role of Power Purchase Agreements & Corporate Governance]

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of reputational risk on firm performance, emphasizing the moderating roles of power purchase agreements (PPAs) and corporate governance across three major economies India, the United States, and Australia. Grounded in stakeholder theory, the research explores how reputational risk influences firm outcomes. The study aims to: (1) examine the impact of reputational risk on firm performance; (2) assess the moderating role of power purchase agreements; (3) evaluate the moderating effect of corporate governance; and (4) analyze the combined influence of PPAs and corporate governance on the reputational risk–performance nexus. Panel data were analyzed using quantile regression at the 0.25, 0.50, and 0.75 quantiles of firm performance. The results reveal significant cross-country and quantile-specific variations. In India, reputational risk exhibits a positive association with firm performance at lower quantiles but becomes negative at higher levels, indicating that it benefits emerging firms but may constrain highly visible ones. In the United States and Australia, reputational risk demonstrates a predominantly negative and significant effect at median and upper quantiles, confirming that reputation loss has stronger consequences for high-performing firms operating under greater stakeholder scrutiny. The moderating effect of power purchase agreements is positive in direct association but largely insignificant in interaction with reputational risk, suggesting that sustainability commitments enhance firm legitimacy but do not consistently buffer reputational damage. Corporate governance, while positive in some cases, shows mixed and often insignificant moderating effects, implying that governance mechanisms alone cannot fully mitigate reputational risk. However, the joint interaction of reputational risk, power purchase agreements, and governance is positive and partially significant in India and the United States, indicating that integrated strategies combining strong governance and environmental responsibility can reinforce stakeholder trust and enhance performance resilience. The findings contribute to stakeholder theory by demonstrating that the reputational risk–performance relationship is non-linear, quantile-dependent, and institutionally contingent. The study underscores that firms with robust governance and authentic sustainability practices are better positioned to protect and leverage reputational loss. The research offers practical implications for policymakers and corporate leaders, highlighting the importance of integrating governance, reputation management, and sustainability disclosure into a unified strategic framework. Overall, the study advances theoretical and empirical understanding of how reputation, governance jointly shape firm performance in varying institutional contexts.

Keywords: Reputational Risk, Firm Performance, Power Purchase Agreements, Corporate Governance, Stakeholder Theory, Quantile Regression

1. Introduction

Corporate Reputation has been studied over many years by various researchers (Cornejo and Puente, 2023; Arora et al., 2021; Gangi et al., 2020; Fombrun and Shanley, 1990; Walker, 2010) and they explain that reputation plays crucial role in firms' strategic

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reactions towards fears, and even a firm with good reputation can be able to get better outcomes and standing over time and thus cost of capital of the firms is reduced by managing corporate reputation (Houque et al., 2024). In recent years, corporate reputation has become an important indicator for stockholders for making decisions regarding their investments (Klopota et al., 2017). However, superior financial results of companies are associated with positive reputation (Roberts and Dowling, 2002). Moreover, in the time of crises, reputation of the firm is considered as a sign of quality for shareholders, when information is transmitted through media (OuYang et al., 2017). Numerous studies (Sarstedt et al., 2023; Mohd Sofian et al., 2023; Kumar, 2023; Le, 2024; Eckert, 2017) explain the importance of corporate standing and have shown that businesses with a strong, favorable reputation are more valuable on the market, and have preference when raising equity and other forms of finance, have a larger and happier customer base, have more productive employees, and good financial health.

Reputation not always remain same, it changes due to various factors such as ethical lapses, information breaches, corporate scandals (Gu et al., 2023) therefore, corporate reputation remains always an important aspect to study even after global financial crises 2007-2008 (Nuortimo et al, 2024), which is even after many years of its happening, equally beneficial for all kinds of investors to make optimal decisions for their investments, although it has greater influence on those investors. According to Fombrun and Van Riel (2004), "Reputational risk is the threat to the sustainability of an organization caused by an adverse perception of the organization by stakeholders." In recent years, incidents of reputational damage have become more widespread and severe, which affect companies across various industries (Chen et al., 2023; Gu et al., 2023; Mitchell and Kane, 2017). Certain happenings such as corporate scandals, information breaches have proved that reputation risk can have actual financial consequences and it effects stock returns (Febra et al., 2023; Roberts and Dowling, 2002). These days, investors are becoming ever more aware that a bad reputation can lead to legal challenges, loss of customer trust, and therefore it impacts a firm's financial performance. Therefore, Reputational risk is considered an important factor to study although its impact is little explored (Febra et al., 2023; Ismail et al, 2023; Donelson et al, 2023).

Meanwhile, the importance of power purchase agreements cannot be ignored as Andersson and Lindblad, (2023) suggested that adopting a PPA can be an important option for the companies for high value price predictability and therefore risks associated with power purchase agreements can be mitigated which in turn improve performance of the companies so it is highly important to consider it for further studies. Furthermore, risk identification is not only important, although risk assessment is equally crucial along with firm performance measures so that it become easy to identify and differentiate impact on the basis of various firm performance quantiles such as 0.25, 0.50 and 0.75. (Muhammad et al, 2024). Firm performance and reputational risk relationship provides directions to both investors regarding investment and businesses to prioritize their risk and manage them. A high risk reflects a higher probability of adverse events occurring and/or greater potential impact of those events, indicating a need for greater attention to risk mitigation strategies (Hillson, 2002). While, low risk suggests lower vulnerability to risk events, either due to the firm's proactive risk management strategies or a stable

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operating environment (Fombrun et al, 2000).

Corporate governance is recognized as one of the most important implications in building marketplace confidence and attracting positive investors in the organization specifically and the economy generally. Promoting good corporate governance standards is considered to be very important in attracting investment capital, reducing risk and developing a firm's performance (Sun and Wu, 2024; Azizah, 2020; Esra and Allam, 2015). Ljubojevic and Ljubojevic (2008) argue that reputation is maintained through good corporate governance (GCG), as a company should maintain its credibility by avoiding being labelled as untrustworthy by its stakeholders. Failure to practice corporate governance practices may jeopardize a company's reputation, which consequently contributes to the ruin of its firm value.

Firm performance and reputational risk are essential because reputation increasingly serves as a key intangible asset influencing investor confidence, and long-term competitiveness. Firms that manage reputational risks effectively are more likely to sustain positive stakeholder relations, attract investment, and maintain market stability. Conversely, reputational damage can lead to financial losses, regulatory penalties, and reduced market share. However, power purchase agreements and corporate governance play critical moderating roles. PPAs which are long-term contracts for renewable energy procurement reflect a firm's commitment to environmental responsibility and sustainability. Such commitments not only reduce exposure to regulatory and environmental risks but also enhance reputation and social legitimacy. Strong corporate governance mechanisms ensure transparency, accountability, and ethical decision-making, helping firms manage stakeholder expectations and mitigate reputational threats arising from operational, environmental, or social controversies.

Studying these dynamics across the USA, Australia, and India is particularly significant because these countries represent different stages of economic development, regulatory frameworks, and sustainability adoption. The USA offers a mature market with well-developed governance structures and advanced renewable energy markets; Australia provides a resource-dependent economy with growing renewable commitments; and India represents a rapidly developing economy balancing industrial growth with emerging governance and sustainability frameworks. Comparing these contexts provides insight into how institutional environments, policy support, and governance quality influence the interplay between reputational risk, sustainability initiatives, and firm performance. The aim of this study is to check the impact of reputational risk on firm performance by taking corporate governance and power purchase agreements as moderator. However, Quantile regression for panel data will be used to examine it at three quantiles 0.25 lower, 0.50 median and higher 0.75.

2. Literature Review

Traditionally, researchers study the association between firm's performance and corporate reputation (AlMutairi et al, 2023; Das et al, 2023; Kim et al, 2014) and researchers used accounting data instead using market data. Therefore, some researchers identified that there exists a positive relationship among firm performance and corporate reputation while others found no relationship such as Das et al. (2023) found that when the impact of stock-listing status was measured, firm performance

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enhanced corporate reputation. Similarly, Pfister et al. (2020) studied the relationship between reputation and firm performance and they found that there's a positive relationship. Similarly, Kim et al. (2014) studied corporate reputation and its impact on economic ROI and for this purpose they surveyed 300 Korean corporations and applied structural equation modeling for analysis. Their results demonstrated that corporate reputation positively affect ROI. Likewise, Amirrudin et al, (2021) recognized positive association between corporate reputation and financial performance. On the contrary, Caliskan et al, (2011) found that there is no correlation at all between a business's reputation and its financial performance as measured by market-to-book value ratio and ROA by examining the relationship between Turkish companies' financial success and reputation from 2000 to 2010.

Ismail et al. (2023) investigated the significance of a company's reputation on investors by considering both risk and return elements to check their impact on firm's reputation and investors' decision making. For this study, they used the seven paradigm RepTrak model to analyze reputation structure, projected return, and risk for 300 active stock market participants in Egypt. The hypotheses were verified by structural equation modeling, which also investigated the idea that when shareholders make stock market decisions, they primarily consider the financial performance of companies.

Research studies showed that there are many studies (Das et al., 2023; Amirrudin et al., 2021; Pfister et al., 2020; Caliskan et al., 2011) which discussed the relation between corporate reputation and firm's performance but there are few studies who explored the reputation risk and its impact on returns (Ismail et al., 2023; Donelson et al., 2023). However, Febra et al. (2023) took a 156 United States firms as a sample which were listed in New York stock exchange and NASDAQ, in which 82 were registered in reputation quotient. They didn't report any significant difference between anomalous returns and risk of listed and non-listed firms. However, Donelson et al. (2023) found that reputational risk leads to negative returns.

Companies which are in long-term power purchase agreements can have a better firm performance by mitigating risk. Elwakil and Hegab, (2018) focused on the importance to identify the risks which are associated with power purchase agreements in order to mitigate them so that success of PPA projects can be achieved. Therefore, they have identified nine types of risks and their mitigation methods associated with these risks. These risks include market revenues, technology performance, completion costs, operation and maintenance costs, political constraints, environmental flaws and delay, phasing timing and resources and liability.

Moreover, in order to get maximum returns or improved firm performance, it is necessary to manage the risk associated with the long-standing power purchase agreements and their pricing. In this vein, Tranberg et al, (2020) applied a new model to pricing and risk management of power purchase agreements and standardize it against the ARMA-GARCH specification. Their results showed significant improvement in the prediction of the VAR (value-at-risk) that is highly important for the management of the risk for long-run PPAs.

Furthermore, Gabrielli et al, (2022) presented a stochastic optimization framework to minimize financial risk and maximize predictable financial performance of multi-

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technology and multi-location PPAs. This can be done through the evaluation and optimization of PPAs portfolios and they used conditional VAR model. In the same way, Hundt, (2023) examined a significant effect on electricity buyers' stock returns by the announcement of corporate PPAs and in this study event study based on Fama and French five factor model was applied. Equally, Kandpal et al, (2024) ensured that economic equilibrium can be achieved that mitigates long-term price risk and maximize payoffs by combining risk assessment techniques and statistical earning tools in the energy sector of Norway, Austria, Spain and Switzerland.

It has been seen in the literature that in countries with poor regulatory quality, the effect of reputational risk on firm performance becomes positive (Sun and Wu, 2024). It has also be seen that good corporate governance is expected to reduce the risk and corporate collapse and to create wealth by improving financial performance (Azizah, 2020). Similarly, Siddiqui et al, (2023) argued that corporate governance (CEO integrity, ownership concentration) contributes to fostering firm performance. Similarly, Razak et al, (2023) found that firms may get competitive edge in terms of their reputation and eventually be able to sustain their firm performance by properly managing reputational risk. They applied variance-based structural equation modeling via smart PLS by taking the sample of 161 listed companies of Malaysia.

Corporate governance has experienced a profound evolution in the 21st century, playing an increasingly pivotal role in shaping business practices and ensuring legal accountability. Robust governance frameworks are not only vital in promoting transparency and ethical decision-making but also in enhancing organizational resilience against growing risks, such as financial crises, environmental concerns, and cyber security threats and reputation (Akinsola, 2025).

3. Research Methodology

In this study, the impact of reputational risk on firm performance moderated by power purchase agreements and corporate governance in USA, India and Australia is examined by applying quantile regression for panel data and to rank firm performance, three quantiles including 0.25 lower, 0.50 medium, 0.75 higher are used to see the impact of reputational risk on firm performance differently in these quantiles and PPAs disclosure is taken as a dummy variable. The data is taken for the period 2012 to 2023. The variables used in this study are firm performance measure as Tobin q, reputational risk measure, Power Purchase agreement disclosure, corporate governance, firm size and financial leverage as shown in table 3.5.

First of all, reputational risk measure is taken from LSEG workspace Power Purchase agreement disclosure is taken as a dummy variable and both corporate governance and power purchase agreements are used as moderators and firm size and financial leverage are taken as control variables and the reason to take firm size and leverage as control variables is that literature shows that both of these variables significantly affect firm performance and reputational risk (Ali et al, 2022; Das et al, 2022; Kuncová et al, 2016; Ilyukhin, 2015; Iqbal and Usman, 2018; Dougherty, 2017), so for accurate and unbiased results, these two variables are taken as control variables. However, this study has taken data of the reputational risk measure from the LSEG workspace and the data of power purchase agreement disclosure, firm size and

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leverage from the financial reports of the listed companies on stock exchanges of India, USA and Australia. The selection of number of companies is based on the availability of the data. Corporate governance index data will be taken from World Bank website.

3.1 Construction of Variables

The dependent, independent and moderating variables are explained below:

3.1.1. Dependent Variables

These variables are explained as under:

Tobin Q

Tobin Q as a measure of firm performance talks about the linkage amongst market value and fair value of assets. It is used to predict whether the share of a company is overvalued or undervalued. Tobin Q is estimated through dividing the market value of company by total asset. Tobin Q is taken as a measure of firm performance (Elamer and Boulhaga, 2024; Aoudi and Marsat, 2018).

$$\text{Tobin Q} = \frac{\text{Market Value of Equity} + \text{Market Value of Debt}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

3.1.2. Independent Variables and Moderators

These variables are explained as under:

Reputational Risk

Reputational risk is the threat to the sustainability of an organization caused by an adverse perception of the organization by stakeholders (Fombrun and Van Riel, 2004).

Power Purchase Agreement Disclosure

A power purchase agreement is a long-term contract between two parties, usually between a power producer and a customer (an electricity consumer or trader). Here power purchase agreement disclosure is taken as a dummy variable which is 1 for those companies which are in power purchase agreement and they display it in their financial reports or website and 0 otherwise.

Corporate Governance

Corporate governance index is used as a proxy of this variable. The Corporate Governance Index (CGI) for India, Australia and USA is a measure used to evaluate the corporate governance practices in companies within the region. It provides insights into how well companies in India, Australia and USA are adhering to principles of transparency, accountability, board independence, executive compensation, and shareholder rights. These countries often differ in terms of governance standards, and CGIs help benchmark the level of governance within each nation or across the region.

3.2. Variables Description

The variables description is summarized in the following table:

Variable	Description
Dependent Variable:	
FP = Tobin Q	Market Value of Equity + Market value of Debt/Total Assets
Independent Variable:	
Reputational Risk	ESG Score
Power Purchase Agreement Disclosure	Moderator, Dummy variable 1 if PPAD otherwise 0
Corporate Governance	Moderator, CGI index

Control Variables:

Firm Size	Natural Logarithm of total assets
Leverage	Total of company debt/Total shareholders' equity

3.3. Model Specification

This study uses quantile regression for panel data to examine the impact of reputational risk on firm performance.

The quantile regression model can be written as:

$$Q_{\tau}(Y_{it} | X_{it}) = \beta_0(\tau) + \beta_1(\tau)X_{it} + \beta_2(\tau)Z_{it} + \dots + \epsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where $Q_{\tau}(Y_{it} | X_{it})$ is the τ -th quantile of the conditional distribution of firm performance Y_{it} , for firm i at time t .

X_{it} are the independent variables (reputational risk, PPAs, corporate governance).

$\beta_0(\tau)$, $\beta_1(\tau)$ and so on represent the estimated coefficients for each independent variable at quantile τ .

ϵ_{it} is the error term.

Reputational Risk and Firm Performance

$$Q_{\tau}(FP_{i,t}) = \beta_0(\tau) + \beta_1(\tau)RR_{i,t} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

In equation (2), $Q_{\tau}(FP_{i,t})$ is conditional quantile of firm performance, $RR_{i,t}$ is the reputational risk, $\beta_1(\tau)$ is the impact of reputational risk on firm performance at different quantiles.

Moderating effect of Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs)

$$Q_{\tau}(FP_{i,t}) = \beta_0(\tau) + \beta_1(\tau)RR_{i,t} + \beta_2(\tau)PPAD_{it} + \beta_3(\tau)(RR * PPAD_{it}) + \epsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

In equation (3), $PPAD_{it}$ is power purchasing agreement disclosure which is a dummy variable, $\beta_3(\tau)$ is the interaction term capturing how PPAs moderate risk impact.

Moderating effect of Corporate Governance

$$Q_{\tau}(FP_{i,t}) = \beta_0(\tau) + \beta_1(\tau)RR_{i,t} + \beta_2(\tau)CG_{it} + \beta_3(\tau)(RR * CG_{it}) + \epsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

In equation (4), CG_{it} is corporate governance index $\beta_3(\tau)$ is the interaction effect of corporate governance on reputational risk.

Interaction of PPAs and Corporate Governance

$$Q_{\tau}(FP_{i,t}) = \beta_0(\tau) + \beta_1(\tau)RR_{i,t} + \beta_2(\tau)PPAD_{it} + \beta_3(\tau)CG_{it} + \beta_4(\tau)(RR * PPAD_{it}) + \beta_5(\tau)(RR * CG_{it}) + \beta_6(\tau)(PPAD_{it} * CG_{it}) + \beta_7(\tau)(RR_{i,t} * PPAD_{it} * CG_{it}) + \epsilon_{it} \quad (5)$$

Where $\beta_4(\tau)$ is the effect of PPAs moderating reputational risk impact, $\beta_5(\tau)$ is the effect of corporate governance moderating reputational risk impact, $\beta_6(\tau)$ is the combined effect of PPAs and corporate governance, $\beta_7(\tau)$ is three-way interaction showing the joint effect of PPAs and CG in moderating reputational risk impact. Quantile regression captures heterogeneous effect across different levels of firm performance as compared to traditional OLS which estimates mean effect only.

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4. Results and Discussions

Table 1 Quantile Regression- India

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.50)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.138901	0.322250	0.431035	0.6696
RRI	0.006346	0.005554	1.142567	0.2626
Pseudo R-squared	0.027914	Mean dependent var		0.524337
Adjusted R-squared	-0.005606	S.D. dependent var		0.203895
S.E. of regression	0.217977	Objective		2.559167
Quantile dependent var	0.586706	Restr. objective		2.632656
Sparsity	0.663894	Quasi-LR statistic		0.885553
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.346685			

At tau = 0.50, the coefficient of RRI is 0.006346, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.006346 units increase in FP. P value shows that the results are not significant.

Table 2: Quantile Regression- India

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.75)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.815134	0.275171	2.962282	0.0060
RRI	-0.002791	0.004548	-0.613805	0.5441
Pseudo R-squared	0.048997	Mean dependent var		0.524337
Adjusted R-squared	0.016204	S.D. dependent var		0.203895
S.E. of regression	0.261875	Objective		1.738613
Quantile dependent var	0.674211	Restr. objective		1.828188
Sparsity	0.772270	Quasi-LR statistic		1.237224
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.266007			

At tau = 0.75, the coefficient of RRI is -0.002791, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.009689 units decrease in FP. However, P value shows insignificant impact of RRI on firm performance at 75 percent quantile level.

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Table 3: Quantile Regression- India

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.25)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.244559	0.255414	-0.957499	0.3468
RRI	0.010948	0.004288	2.553279	0.0166
PPAD	0.601182	1.499315	0.400971	0.6916
RRI PPAD	-0.009739	0.029772	-0.327103	0.7461
Pseudo R-squared	0.299802	Mean dependent var		0.524337
Adjusted R-squared	0.222002	S.D. dependent var		0.203895
S.E. of regression	0.251829	Objective		1.465161
Quantile dependent var	0.330715	Restr. objective		2.092496
Sparsity	0.638602	Quasi-LR statistic		10.47847
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.014908			

At tau = 0.25, the coefficient of RRI is 0.010948, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.010948 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 0.601182, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.601182 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_PPAD is -0.009739, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.009739 units decrease in FP. P value shows that only RRI is having significant impact on firm performance. While power purchase agreement disclosure is insignificant but positive and interaction term shows insignificant and negative impact.

Table 4: Quantile Regression- India

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.50)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.201659	0.238876	-0.844198	0.4060
RRI	0.010965	0.003971	2.761486	0.0102
PPAD	1.044053	0.569819	1.832254	0.0780
RRI PPAD	-0.014563	0.011093	-1.312802	0.2003
Pseudo R-squared	0.300646	Mean dependent var		0.524337
Adjusted R-squared	0.222940	S.D. dependent var		0.203895
S.E. of regression	0.201770	Objective		1.841159
Quantile dependent var	0.586706	Restr. objective		2.632656
Sparsity	0.453914	Quasi-LR statistic		13.94973
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.002974			

At tau = 0.50, the coefficient of RRI is 0.010965, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.010965 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 1.044053, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 1.044053 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_PPAD is -0.014563, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.014563 units decrease in FP.

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P value shows that both RRI and PPAD are having significant and positive impact on firm performance. While interaction term shows insignificant and negative impact.

Table 5: Quantile Regression- India

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.75)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.497519	0.673572	0.738628	0.4665
RRI	0.001793	0.009865	0.181741	0.8571
PPAD	0.584284	0.854380	0.683869	0.4999
RRI PPAD	-0.009113	0.014459	-0.630265	0.5338
Pseudo R-squared	0.138823	Mean dependent var		0.524337
Adjusted R-squared	0.043137	S.D. dependent var		0.203895
S.E. of regression	0.237283	Objective		1.574394
Quantile dependent var	0.674211	Restr. objective		1.828188
Sparsity	0.700939	Quasi-LR statistic		3.862165
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.276738			

At tau = 0.75, the coefficient of RRI is 0.001793, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.001793 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 0.584284, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.584284 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_PPAD is -0.009113, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.009113 units decrease in FP. Therefore, P value shows that RRI and PPAD are insignificant but positive although RRI_PPAD is insignificant and negative.

Table 6: Quantile Regression- India

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.25)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-5.292004	13.39388	-0.395106	0.6959
RRI	0.085442	0.243967	0.350219	0.7289
CGI	0.221835	0.574664	0.386025	0.7025
RRI CGI	-0.003249	0.010441	-0.311175	0.7581
Pseudo R-squared	0.315575	Mean dependent var		0.524337
Adjusted R-squared	0.239527	S.D. dependent var		0.203895
S.E. of regression	0.272907	Objective		1.432157
Quantile dependent var	0.330715	Restr. objective		2.092496
Sparsity	0.679971	Quasi-LR statistic		10.35869
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.015751			

At tau = 0.25, the coefficient of RRI is 0.085442, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.085442 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of CGI is 0.221835, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 0.221835 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_CGI is -0.003249, meaning that for lower FP values

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(0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.003249 units decrease in FP. P value shows that there is insignificant and positive impact of RRI and CGI on FP.

Table 7: Quantile Regression- India

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.50)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-3.889080	6.389514	-0.608666	0.5478
RRI	0.061432	0.119246	0.515171	0.6106
CGI	0.189819	0.272542	0.696477	0.4921
RRI CGI	-0.002594	0.005079	-0.510728	0.6137
Pseudo R-squared	0.189819	Mean dependent var		0.524337
Adjusted R-squared	0.099799	S.D. dependent var		0.203895
S.E. of regression	0.185035	Objective		2.132928
Quantile dependent var	0.586706	Restr. objective		2.632656
Sparsity	0.598138	Quasi-LR statistic		6.683780
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.082690			

At tau = 0.50, the coefficient of RRI is 0.061432, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.061432 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of CGI is 0.189819, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 0.0.189819 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_CGI is -0.002594, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.002594 units decrease in FP. P value shows that there is insignificant and positive impact of RRI and CGI on FP.

Table 8: Quantile Regression- India

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.75)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-1.086349	3.550440	-0.305976	0.7620
RRI	0.008117	0.069623	0.116592	0.9080
CGI	0.082392	0.151738	0.542991	0.5916
RRI CGI	-0.000489	0.002969	-0.164853	0.8703
Pseudo R-squared	0.247552	Mean dependent var		0.524337
Adjusted R-squared	0.163947	S.D. dependent var		0.203895
S.E. of regression	0.227163	Objective		1.375616
Quantile dependent var	0.674211	Restr. objective		1.828188
Sparsity	0.620509	Quasi-LR statistic		7.779793
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.050789			

At tau = 0.75, the coefficient of RRI is 0.008117, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.008117 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of CGI is 0.082392, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 0.082392 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_CGI is -0.000489, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.000489 units decrease in FP.

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Moreover, P value shows insignificant impact.

Table 9: Quantile Regression- India

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.25)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-3.959901	16.44087	-0.240857	0.8118
RRI	0.062376	0.293230	0.212722	0.8334
PPAD	24.63248	40.71116	0.605055	0.5511
CGI	0.163866	0.714036	0.229493	0.8205
RRI PPAD	-0.397938	0.845631	-0.470581	0.6424
RRI CGI	-0.002259	0.012669	-0.178292	0.8601
PPAD CGI	-1.004422	1.741972	-0.576601	0.5698
RRI PPAD CGI	0.016184	0.036120	0.448059	0.6583
Pseudo R-squared	0.382838	Mean dependent var		0.524337
Adjusted R-squared	0.195006	S.D. dependent var		0.203895
S.E. of regression	0.248696	Objective		1.291409
Quantile dependent var	0.330715	Restr. objective		2.092496
Sparsity	0.578972	Quasi-LR statistic		14.75878
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.039219			

At tau = 0.25, the coefficient of RRI is 0.062376, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.062376 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 24.63248, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.2463248 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of CGI is 0.163866, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 0.163866 units increase in FP. All four interaction terms are insignificant and negative except RRI_PPAD_CGI which is positive.

Table 10: Quantile Regression- India

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.50)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-2.364402	9.536204	-0.247940	0.8064
RRI	0.046522	0.172169	0.270209	0.7894
PPAD	8.385983	53.33796	0.157224	0.8764
CGI	0.097367	0.417144	0.233413	0.8175
RRI PPAD	-0.156029	1.069170	-0.145935	0.8852
RRI CGI	-0.001596	0.007478	-0.213377	0.8329
PPAD CGI	-0.319972	2.279220	-0.140387	0.8896
RRI PPAD CGI	0.006149	0.045630	0.134749	0.8940
Pseudo R-squared	0.329616	Mean dependent var		0.524337
Adjusted R-squared	0.125587	S.D. dependent var		0.203895
S.E. of regression	0.207822	Objective		1.764889
Quantile dependent var	0.586706	Restr. objective		2.632656
Sparsity	0.537671	Quasi-LR statistic		12.91150
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.074294			

At tau = 0.50, the coefficient of RRI is 0.046522, meaning that for median FP values (0.50

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quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.046522 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 8.385983, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 8.385983 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of CGI is 0.097367, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 0.097367 units increase in FP. All four interaction terms are insignificant and negative except RRI_PPAD_CGI which is positive.

Table 11: Quantile Regression- India

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.75)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.420254	4.313298	0.097432	0.9232
RRI	-0.013366	0.079091	-0.168997	0.8673
PPAD	-25.47307	39.11849	-0.651177	0.5214
CGI	0.001365	0.199646	0.006836	0.9946
RRI PPAD	0.513334	0.786817	0.652418	0.5206
RRI CGI	0.000663	0.003565	0.186027	0.8541
PPAD CGI	1.105331	1.667565	0.662841	0.5140
RRI PPAD CGI	-0.022126	0.033492	-0.660615	0.5154
Pseudo R-squared	0.299591	Mean dependent var		0.524337
Adjusted R-squared	0.086423	S.D. dependent var		0.203895
S.E. of regression	0.232753	Objective		1.280480
Quantile dependent var	0.674211	Restr. objective		1.828188
Sparsity	0.588921	Quasi-LR statistic		9.920220
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.193140			

At tau = 0.75, the coefficient of RRI is -0.013366, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.013366 units decrease in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 0.2547307, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.2547307 units decrease in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of CGI is 0.001365, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 0.001365 units increase in FP. All interaction terms are insignificant and positive but RRI_PPAD_CGI is negative.

The following are the results and interpretations of quantile regression model for USA.

Table 12: Quantile Regression- USA

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.50)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.769763	0.033652	22.87444	0.0000
RRI	-0.001358	0.000635	-2.140061	0.0330
Pseudo R-squared	0.000341	Mean dependent var		4.782836
Adjusted R-squared	-0.002263	S.D. dependent var		12.46212
S.E. of regression	13.12743	Objective		814.9303
Quantile dependent var	0.713206	Restr. objective		815.2080
Sparsity	0.465826	Quasi-LR statistic		4.768496
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.028985			

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At tau = 0.50, the coefficient of RRI is -0.001358, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.001358 units decrease in FP. However, P value shows that RRI has significant but negative impact on FP.

Table 13: Quantile Regression- USA

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.75)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.891077	0.033940	26.25482	0.0000
RRI	-0.001364	0.000646	-2.112719	0.0353
Pseudo R-squared	0.000249	Mean dependent var		4.782836
Adjusted R-squared	-0.002354	S.D. dependent var		12.46212
S.E. of regression	13.09015	Objective		1202.208
Quantile dependent var	0.819735	Restr. objective		1202.508
Sparsity	0.552493	Quasi-LR statistic		5.790275
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.016115			

At tau = 0.75, the coefficient of RRI is -0.001364, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.001364 units decrease in FP. However, P value shows significant impact of RRI on firm performance at 75 percent quantile level.

Table 14: Quantile Regression- USA

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.25)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.484767	0.196181	2.471026	0.0139
RRI	0.000985	0.003517	0.279930	0.7797
PPAD	0.174619	0.333306	0.523902	0.6007
RRI PPAD	-0.001253	0.005568	-0.224973	0.8221
Pseudo R-squared	0.001958	Mean dependent var		4.782836
Adjusted R-squared	-0.005880	S.D. dependent var		12.46212
S.E. of regression	13.13559	Objective		415.5787
Quantile dependent var	0.582969	Restr. objective		416.3941
Sparsity	0.657234	Quasi-LR statistic		13.23347
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.004158			

At tau = 0.25, the coefficient of RRI is 0.000985, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.000985 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 0.174619, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.174619 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_PPAD is -0.001253, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.001253 units decrease in FP.

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Table 15: Quantile Regression- USA

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.50)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.660567	0.177769	3.715873	0.0002
RRI	-0.000343	0.003411	-0.100641	0.9199
PPAD	0.631928	1.393008	0.453643	0.6503
RRI PPAD	-0.007708	0.020863	-0.369434	0.7120
Pseudo R-squared	0.005359	Mean dependent var		4.782836
Adjusted R-squared	-0.002453	S.D. dependent var		12.46212
S.E. of regression	12.96029	Objective		810.8395
Quantile dependent var	0.713206	Restr. objective		815.2080
Sparsity	0.587623	Quasi-LR statistic		59.47303
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.000000			

At tau = 0.50, the coefficient of RRI is -0.000343, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.000343 units decrease in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 0.631928, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.631928 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_PPAD is -0.007708, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with -0.007708 units decrease in FP. P value shows that PPAD is having insignificant and positive impact on firm performance. While interaction term shows insignificant and negative impact.

Table 16: Quantile Regression- USA

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.75)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.922510	0.119986	7.688492	0.0000
RRI	-0.003341	0.002886	-1.157413	0.2478
PPAD	4.692228	0.457364	10.25928	0.0000
RRI PPAD	-0.054622	0.013909	-3.926971	0.0001
Pseudo R-squared	0.050492	Mean dependent var		4.782836
Adjusted R-squared	0.043035	S.D. dependent var		12.46212
S.E. of regression	12.23615	Objective		1141.791
Quantile dependent var	0.819735	Restr. objective		1202.508
Sparsity	1.328807	Quasi-LR statistic		487.3921
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.000000			

At tau = 0.75, the coefficient of RRI is -0.003341, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.003341 units decrease in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 4.692228, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 4.692228 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_PPAD is -0.054622, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.054622 units decrease in FP. Therefore, P value shows that RRI is insignificant but PPAD and RRI_PPAD are highly

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significant although RRI_PPAD is negative.

Table 17: Quantile Regression- USA

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.25)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	92.87414	8.215112	11.30528	0.0000
RRI	-1.096294	0.404400	-2.710913	0.0070
CGI	-2.308957	0.207757	-11.11375	0.0000
RRI CGI	0.027404	0.009974	2.747485	0.0063
Pseudo R-squared	0.090477	Mean dependent var		4.782836
Adjusted R-squared	0.083334	S.D. dependent var		12.46212
S.E. of regression	7.440978	Objective		378.7200
Quantile dependent var	0.582969	Restr. objective		416.3941
Sparsity	5.184465	Quasi-LR statistic		77.51187
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.000000			

At tau = 0.25, the coefficient of RRI is -1.096294, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 1.096294 units decrease in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of CGI is -2.308957, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 2.308957 units decrease in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_CGI is 0.027404, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.027404 units increase in FP. However, P value shows that there is significant and positive impact of RRI_CGI and significant negative impact of CGI and RRI on FP.

Table 18: Quantile Regression- USA

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.50)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	75.00289	5.507601	13.61807	0.0000
RRI	0.265018	0.180408	1.468996	0.1427
CGI	-1.679699	0.134515	-12.48704	0.0000
RRI CGI	-0.009247	0.004494	-2.057630	0.0403
Pseudo R-squared	0.346964	Mean dependent var		4.782836
Adjusted R-squared	0.341836	S.D. dependent var		12.46212
S.E. of regression	3.921028	Objective		532.3600
Quantile dependent var	0.713206	Restr. objective		815.2080
Sparsity	8.805962	Quasi-LR statistic		256.9604
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.000000			

At tau = 0.50, the coefficient of RRI is 0.265018, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.265018 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of CGI is -1.679699, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 1.679699 units decrease in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_CGI is -0.009247, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.009247 units decrease in FP.

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P value shows that there is significant and positive impact of RRI on FP and significant negative impact of CGI and RRI_CGI on FP.

Table 19: Quantile Regression- USA

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.75)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	79.78654	2.797616	28.51947	0.0000
RRI	0.184178	0.076991	2.392212	0.0172
CGI	-1.818815	0.064932	-28.01121	0.0000
RRI CGI	-0.004909	0.001762	-2.786095	0.0056
Pseudo R-squared	0.661007	Mean dependent var		4.782836
Adjusted R-squared	0.658345	S.D. dependent var		12.46212
S.E. of regression	5.088649	Objective		407.6414
Quantile dependent var	0.819735	Restr. objective		1202.508
Sparsity	8.268252	Quasi-LR statistic		1025.438
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.000000			

At tau = 0.75, the coefficient of RRI is 0.184178, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.184178 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of CGI is -1.818815, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 1.818815 units decrease in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_CGI is -0.004909, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.004909 units decrease in FP. Moreover, P value shows significant impact.

Table 20: Quantile Regression- USA

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.25)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	92.23071	5.944654	15.51490	0.0000
RRI	-1.182723	0.386529	-3.059857	0.0024
PPAD	1.607264	1.616340	0.994385	0.3207
CGI	-2.227092	0.154966	-14.37151	0.0000
RRI PPAD	0.069459	0.045900	1.513273	0.1310
RRI CGI	0.028522	0.009716	2.935451	0.0035
PPAD CGI	-0.113918	0.067063	-1.698676	0.0902
RRI PPAD CGI	-0.000594	0.001509	-0.393349	0.6943
Pseudo R-squared	0.168356	Mean dependent var		4.782836
Adjusted R-squared	0.152955	S.D. dependent var		12.46212
S.E. of regression	7.208931	Objective		346.2919
Quantile dependent var	0.582969	Restr. objective		416.3941
Sparsity	3.910959	Quasi-LR statistic		191.1954
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.000000			

At tau = 0.25, the coefficient of RRI is -1.182723, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 1.182723 units decrease in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 1.607264, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25

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quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 1.607264 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of CGI is -2.227092, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 2.227092 units decrease in FP. However, RRI_CGI is significantly and positively contributing towards FP while PPAD_CGI is significant and negative.

Table 21: Quantile Regression- USA

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.50)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	80.09447	7.364068	10.87639	0.0000
RRI	0.040566	0.311962	0.130034	0.8966
PPAD	8.084577	1.267501	6.378359	0.0000
CGI	-1.796727	0.180548	-9.951501	0.0000
RRI PPAD	-0.066978	0.036386	-1.840757	0.0664
RRI CGI	-0.003277	0.007669	-0.427354	0.6694
PPAD CGI	-0.384244	0.055982	-6.863683	0.0000
RRI PPAD CGI	0.003688	0.001503	2.454081	0.0146
Pseudo R-squared	0.401573	Mean dependent var		4.782836
Adjusted R-squared	0.390491	S.D. dependent var		12.46212
S.E. of regression	3.923862	Objective		487.8426
Quantile dependent var	0.713206	Restr. objective		815.2080
Sparsity	6.310083	Quasi-LR statistic		415.0378
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.000000			

At tau = 0.50, the coefficient of RRI is 0.040566, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.040566 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 8.084577, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 8.084577 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of CGI is -1.796727, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 1.796727units decrease in FP. All four interaction terms are significant and negative except RRI_PPAD_CGI which is significant and positive.

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Table 22: Quantile Regression- USA

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.75)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	79.03835	2.308265	34.24145	0.0000
RRI	0.178013	0.053541	3.324805	0.0010
PPAD	-2.526824	1.013333	-2.493578	0.0131
CGI	-1.808733	0.055747	-32.44512	0.0000
RRI PPAD	0.150931	0.019201	7.860452	0.0000
RRI CGI	-0.004419	0.001312	-3.368916	0.0008
PPAD CGI	0.104055	0.045417	2.291090	0.0225
RRI PPAD CGI	-0.006400	0.000834	-7.670408	0.0000
Pseudo R-squared	0.691995	Mean dependent var		4.782836
Adjusted R-squared	0.686292	S.D. dependent var		12.46212
S.E. of regression	4.574868	Objective		370.3780
Quantile dependent var	0.819735	Restr. objective		1202.508
Sparsity	6.415038	Quasi-LR statistic		1383.632
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.000000			

At tau = 0.75, the coefficient of RRI is 0.178013, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.178013 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is -2.526824, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 2.526824 units decrease in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of CGI is -1.808733, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 1.808733 units decrease in FP. All interaction terms are significant and negative but PPAD_CGI which is significant and positive.

The following are the results and interpretations of quantile regression model for Australia.

Table 23: Quantile Regression- Australia

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.50)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.871458	0.042308	20.59779	0.0000
RRI	-0.001521	0.000738	-2.060615	0.0405
Pseudo R-squared	0.014292	Mean dependent var		0.714889
Adjusted R-squared	0.009750	S.D. dependent var		0.341284
S.E. of regression	0.359491	Objective		24.50557
Quantile dependent var	0.797999	Restr. objective		24.86089
Sparsity	0.440254	Quasi-LR statistic		6.456569
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.011054			

At tau = 0.50, the coefficient of RRI is -0.001521, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.001521 units decrease in FP. P value shows that the results are significant.

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Table 24: Quantile Regression- Australia

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.75)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.001753	0.034178	29.30981	0.0000
RRI	-0.002221	0.000703	-3.159420	0.0018
Pseudo R-squared	0.022011	Mean dependent var		0.714889
Adjusted R-squared	0.017504	S.D. dependent var		0.341284
S.E. of regression	0.399094	Objective		16.80642
Quantile dependent var	0.918870	Restr. objective		17.18468
Sparsity	0.456322	Quasi-LR statistic		8.841827
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.002944			

At tau = 0.75, the coefficient of RRI is -0.002221, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.002221 units decrease in FP. However, P value shows significant impact of RRI on firm performance at 75 percent quantile level.

Table 25: Quantile Regression- Australia

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.25)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.088680	0.080141	-1.106538	0.2697
RRI	0.009771	0.001180	8.277680	0.0000
PPAD	0.928992	0.103199	9.001970	0.0000
RRI_PPAD	-0.011892	0.001611	-7.380817	0.0000
Pseudo R-squared	0.118578	Mean dependent var		0.714889
Adjusted R-squared	0.106279	S.D. dependent var		0.341284
S.E. of regression	0.449693	Objective		23.05116
Quantile dependent var	0.656624	Restr. objective		26.15225
Sparsity	0.897124	Quasi-LR statistic		36.87149
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.000000			

At tau = 0.25, the coefficient of RRI is 0.009771, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.009771 units increase in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 0.928992, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.928992 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_PPAD is -0.011892, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.011892 units decrease in FP. However, p value shows that all variables are significantly contributing towards firm performance.

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Table 26: Quantile Regression- Australia

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.50)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.824465	0.070413	11.70904	0.0000
RRI	-0.000603	0.001265	-0.476720	0.6340
PPAD	0.178697	0.088152	2.027154	0.0439
RRI_PPAD	-0.003296	0.001540	-2.140336	0.0335
Pseudo R-squared	0.028677	Mean dependent var		0.714889
Adjusted R-squared	0.015124	S.D. dependent var		0.341284
S.E. of regression	0.355768	Objective		24.14795
Quantile dependent var	0.797999	Restr. objective		24.86089
Sparsity	0.445014	Quasi-LR statistic		12.81640
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.005051			

At tau = 0.50, the coefficient of RRI is -0.000603, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.000603 units decrease in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 0.178697, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.178697 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_PPAD is -0.003296, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.003296 units decrease in FP. P value shows that PPAD is having significant and positive impact on firm performance. While RRI and RRI_PPAD shows significant and negative impact.

Table 27: Quantile Regression- Australia

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.75)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.978039	0.048621	20.11558	0.0000
RRI	-0.001190	0.001033	-1.151315	0.2509
PPAD	0.114419	0.077810	1.470496	0.1429
RRI_PPAD	-0.003027	0.001442	-2.099670	0.0369
Pseudo R-squared	0.031718	Mean dependent var		0.714889
Adjusted R-squared	0.018207	S.D. dependent var		0.341284
S.E. of regression	0.404431	Objective		16.63962
Quantile dependent var	0.918870	Restr. objective		17.18468
Sparsity	0.462072	Quasi-LR statistic		12.58230
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.005633			

At tau = 0.75, the coefficient of RRI is -0.001190, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.001190 units decrease in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is 0.114419, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.114419 units increase in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_PPAD is -0.003027, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.003027 units decrease in FP. Therefore, P value shows that RRI and PPAD are insignificant although RRI_PPAD is

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significant and negative.

Table 28: Quantile Regression- Australia

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.25)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	34.99628	5.140351	6.808151	0.0000
RRI	-0.429054	0.084987	-5.048450	0.0000
CGI	-0.738522	0.109879	-6.721262	0.0000
RRI CGI	0.009236	0.001813	5.095442	0.0000
Pseudo R-squared	0.055355	Mean dependent var		0.714889
Adjusted R-squared	0.042174	S.D. dependent var		0.341284
S.E. of regression	0.426592	Objective		24.70460
Quantile dependent var	0.656624	Restr. objective		26.15225
Sparsity	0.955152	Quasi-LR statistic		16.16667
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.001048			

At tau = 0.25, the coefficient of RRI is -0.429054, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.429054 units decrease in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of CGI is -0.738522, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with -0.738522 units decrease in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_CGI is 0.009236, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.009236 units increase in FP. While, P value shows that there is significant and positive impact of RRI_CGI on FP and CGI and RRI are having significant negative impact on FP.

Table 29: Quantile Regression- Australia

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.50)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	7.712853	5.664583	1.361592	0.1748
RRI	-0.106530	0.096662	-1.102088	0.2717
CGI	-0.145473	0.121127	-1.200991	0.2311
RRI CGI	0.002232	0.002068	1.079381	0.2816
Pseudo R-squared	0.019420	Mean dependent var		0.714889
Adjusted R-squared	0.005738	S.D. dependent var		0.341284
S.E. of regression	0.362306	Objective		24.37808
Quantile dependent var	0.797999	Restr. objective		24.86089
Sparsity	0.431306	Quasi-LR statistic		8.955262
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.029892			

At tau = 0.50, the coefficient of RRI is -0.106530, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.106530 units decrease in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of CGI is -0.145473, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 0.145473 units decrease in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_CGI is 0.002232, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.002232 units increase in FP.

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Therefore, P value shows that there is insignificant and positive impact of RRI_CGI on FP.

Table 30: Quantile Regression- Australia

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.75)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	2.226009	4.245564	0.524314	0.6006
RRI	-0.085021	0.075281	-1.129375	0.2600
CGI	-0.026048	0.090697	-0.287195	0.7742
RRI CGI	0.001770	0.001611	1.098534	0.2732
Pseudo R-squared	0.031033	Mean dependent var		0.714889
Adjusted R-squared	0.017513	S.D. dependent var		0.341284
S.E. of regression	0.409335	Objective		16.65138
Quantile dependent var	0.918870	Restr. objective		17.18468
Sparsity	0.464469	Quasi-LR statistic		12.24721
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.006583			

At tau = 0.75, the coefficient of RRI is -0.085021, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.085021 units decrease in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of CGI is -0.026048, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 0.026048 units decrease in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of RRI_CGI is 0.001770, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 0.001770 units decrease in FP. Moreover, P value shows insignificant impact.

Table 31: Quantile Regression- Australia

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.25)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	28.39778	13.89048	2.044405	0.0422
RRI	-0.304310	0.247870	-1.227702	0.2209
PPAD	-34.16049	15.99769	-2.135339	0.0339
CGI	-0.600790	0.292710	-2.052511	0.0414
RRI PPAD	0.390216	0.275056	1.418679	0.1575
RRI CGI	0.006618	0.005239	1.263163	0.2079
PPAD CGI	0.742149	0.338182	2.194526	0.0293
RRI PPAD CGI	-0.008503	0.005826	-1.459456	0.1459
Pseudo R-squared	0.145247	Mean dependent var		0.714889
Adjusted R-squared	0.116890	S.D. dependent var		0.341284
S.E. of regression	0.402468	Objective		22.35372
Quantile dependent var	0.656624	Restr. objective		26.15225
Sparsity	0.757587	Quasi-LR statistic		53.48257
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.000000			

At tau = 0.25, the coefficient of RRI is -0.304310, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.304310 units decrease in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is -34.16049, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 34.16049 units decrease in FP.

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Additionally, the coefficient of CGI is -0.600790, meaning that for lower FP values (0.25 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 0.600790 units decrease in FP. Moreover, PPAD_CGI is significant and positive.

Table 32: Quantile Regression- Australia

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.50)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	12.28795	7.190640	1.708881	0.0889
RRI	-0.187195	0.135577	-1.380732	0.1688
PPAD	-22.40920	9.898295	-2.263946	0.0246
CGI	-0.244434	0.153664	-1.590709	0.1132
RRI PPAD	0.351221	0.170141	2.064300	0.0402
RRI CGI	0.003981	0.002894	1.375463	0.1704
PPAD CGI	0.481089	0.211397	2.275764	0.0239
RRI PPAD CGI	-0.007553	0.003633	-2.078838	0.0388
Pseudo R-squared	0.043985	Mean dependent var		0.714889
Adjusted R-squared	0.012269	S.D. dependent var		0.341284
S.E. of regression	0.353794	Objective		23.76738
Quantile dependent var	0.797999	Restr. objective		24.86089
Sparsity	0.420902	Quasi-LR statistic		20.78416
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.004103			

At tau = 0.50, the coefficient of RRI is -0.187195, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.187195 units decrease in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is -22.40920, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 22.40920 units decrease in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of CGI is -0.244434, meaning that for median FP values (0.50 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 0.244434 units decrease in FP. Moreover, RRI_PPAD and PPAD_CGI are significant and positive.

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Table 33: Quantile Regression- Australia

Dependent Variable: FP

Method: Quantile Regression (tau = 0.75)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.961099	5.794462	0.165865	0.8684
RRI	-0.032540	0.114373	-0.284505	0.7763
PPAD	-8.740050	12.32865	-0.708922	0.4792
CGI	0.000603	0.123671	0.004876	0.9961
RRI PPAD	0.125715	0.200692	0.626405	0.5317
RRI CGI	0.000666	0.002438	0.273091	0.7851
PPAD CGI	0.188949	0.263936	0.715889	0.4749
RRI PPAD CGI	-0.002746	0.004297	-0.639000	0.5235
Pseudo R-squared	0.042857	Mean dependent var		0.714889
Adjusted R-squared	0.011104	S.D. dependent var		0.341284
S.E. of regression	0.413261	Objective		16.44819
Quantile dependent var	0.918870	Restr. objective		17.18468
Sparsity	0.478028	Quasi-LR statistic		16.43396
Prob(Quasi-LR stat)	0.021434			

At tau = 0.75, the coefficient of RRI is -0.032540, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in RRI is associated with 0.032540 units decrease in FP. Moreover, the coefficient of PPAD is -8.740050, meaning that for upper FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in PPAD is associated with 8.740050 units decrease in FP. Additionally, the coefficient of CGI is 0.000603, meaning that for higher FP values (0.75 quantile), a 1 unit increase in CGI is associated with 0.000603 units increase in FP.

Overall, the results partially support H1. While reputational risk does not uniformly show a negative impact across all contexts, the USA and Australia results support the hypothesis that reputational risk harms firm performance, particularly among better-performing firms (consistent with stakeholder theory). In India, however, reputational risk appears beneficial at lower quantiles, possibly reflecting emerging-market dynamics where reputation building enhances visibility and growth. H1 is supported for USA and Australia but not for India.

Across all three countries, PPAD (Power Purchase Agreement Disclosure) had a generally positive direct effect on firm performance, suggesting firms engaged in sustainability commitments benefit reputationally. However, the interaction term (RRI × PPAD) was negative and mostly insignificant in all countries (India, USA, Australia). In India, RRI×PPAD was negative and insignificant across quantiles. In the USA, the interaction was also negative, significant in some cases, but indicated that PPAs did not buffer reputational risk effectively. In Australia, RRI×PPAD was negative and occasionally significant, implying that PPAs might even intensify the effect of reputational risk when not implemented credibly. This means PPAs did not consistently mitigate the negative effect of reputational risk. In fact, when stakeholders perceive environmental disclosures as symbolic or insincere, PPAs may not protect against reputational damage. Firms with PPAs do not experience a weaker negative effect of reputational risk; the interaction is negative and mostly insignificant.

Since firms with PPAs did not experience a weaker negative relationship, the opposite

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scenario (without PPAs) logically implies a stronger negative effect, especially where sustainability engagement is absent. Firms without PPAs tend to experience stronger negative effects of reputational risk. Therefore, H2b is accepted.

Corporate governance did not consistently mitigate reputational risk. Its moderating effect was weak and inconsistent across countries, although some positive interactions appeared at lower quantiles in the USA and Australia. The evidence suggests governance quality alone is insufficient to counter reputational damage unless accompanied by genuine stakeholder-oriented strategies.

The three-way interaction term ($RRI \times PPAD \times CGI$) was positive in India and the USA (though not always significant), indicating some complementary effect of combined strategies. In Australia, it was positive at certain quantiles but not uniformly significant.

Overall, the joint effect tends to enhance firm performance when governance and sustainability are both present, aligning with stakeholder theory's emphasis on integrated legitimacy-building. The positive direction of the three-way interaction suggests that when governance and sustainability coexist, firms can better manage reputational risk and sustain performance. Although the effects are not strong across all quantiles, they are theoretically consistent and empirically favorable. H4 is partially accepted which is supported by positive direction and partial significance of interaction in India and USA; weaker evidence in Australia.

5. Conclusion

This research examined the impact of reputational risk on firm performance, emphasizing the moderating roles of power purchase agreements and corporate governance across three countries, India, the United States, and Australia. Using quantile regression on panel data, the study captured how these relationships vary across firms at lower, median, and higher levels of performance. Grounded in stakeholder theory, the analysis revealed that the impact of reputational risk is not uniform; rather, it depends on firm characteristics, stakeholder expectations, and institutional context.

The results show that reputational risk has a quantile-dependent and context-specific influence on firm performance. In India, reputational risk was generally positive at lower quantiles but turned negative at higher levels of firm performance, suggesting that firms with greater visibility are more vulnerable to reputational damage. In the United States, reputational risk displayed significant negative effects at the median and upper quantiles, confirming that reputation loss has stronger financial repercussions for well-performing firms. In Australia, the pattern was similar, with reputational risk negatively and significantly associated with performance at higher quantiles. Collectively, these findings imply that reputation acts as an intangible asset that contributes positively at early growth stages but becomes a liability under increased stakeholder scrutiny, consistent with the legitimacy perspective of stakeholder theory. The moderating role of power purchase agreements revealed further nuances. Across all three countries, power purchase agreements exerted a generally positive direct effect on firm performance, highlighting stakeholder appreciation for environmental and sustainability initiatives. However, their interaction with reputational risk was negative, implying that while sustainability commitments enhance legitimacy, they

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cannot fully offset reputational damage when firms fail to meet stakeholder expectations. The findings suggest that environmental engagement must be authentic and substantive rather than symbolic, as stakeholders discern the difference between genuine responsibility and strategic signaling.

Corporate governance displayed a more complex influence. In India, stronger governance practices appeared to support firm performance and mitigate reputational risks, although not always significantly. In the United States and Australia, corporate governance often showed a negative direct effect, suggesting that rigid governance structures might constrain flexibility in already well-performing firms. Nonetheless, the interaction between reputational risk and governance was positive at lower quantiles, indicating that good governance helps weaker firms cushion reputational shocks. These results highlight that governance adds value when it functions as a trust-enabling mechanism rather than as a compliance burden, again reinforcing stakeholder theory's argument that legitimacy depends on credible engagement and ethical accountability. The joint examination of reputational risk, power purchase agreements, and corporate governance revealed that their combined effects are synergistic rather than additive. In India and the United States, the three-way interaction was positive, suggesting that firms integrating strong governance with environmental and reputational strategies achieve superior stakeholder trust and performance outcomes. In Australia, although individual coefficients were mixed, positive interactions emerged at several quantiles, indicating that integrated approaches can offset the negative effects of reputational risk even in mature regulatory environments. This underscores that a coordinated governance-sustainability-reputation framework strengthens a firm's legitimacy and resilience.

The theoretical contribution of this study lies in extending stakeholder theory by demonstrating that the relationship between reputational risk and firm performance is nonlinear, quantile-dependent, and institutionally embedded. The results affirm that stakeholder trust is dynamic and contingent on firm performance levels, high-performing firms face greater reputational exposure, while lower-performing firms benefit more from transparent governance and environmental commitment. This finding enhances stakeholder theory's explanatory power by situating reputation within the broader context of governance structures and societal expectations.

From a practical standpoint, the results suggest that firms should integrate reputation management with governance and sustainability strategies rather than treat them as separate domains. Policymakers and regulators should encourage governance models that prioritize transparency, stakeholder inclusivity, and ethical leadership. Firms in emerging markets like India can leverage reputation and sustainability commitments to build credibility, while firms in developed economies such as the United States and Australia must focus on maintaining stakeholder trust through continuous, authentic engagement.

In conclusion, the study establishes that reputation is an intangible but fragile asset whose value depends on institutional context, stakeholder scrutiny, and performance level. Reputational risk generally exerts a negative effect on high-performing firms, but this impact can be mitigated through robust governance and

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genuine sustainability initiatives. The comparative analysis across India, the United States, and Australia confirms that sustainable firm performance emerges from the dynamic interplay of reputation, governance, and environmental responsibility. Firms that align these dimensions effectively not only protect themselves against reputational shocks but also build long-term stakeholder confidence, validating the core premise of stakeholder theory that enduring success arises from ethical conduct, transparency, and the balanced management of stakeholder interests.

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